

Original Article

Effect of ALP (adaptive learning framework) on students' cognitive abilities in Gujrat, Punjab, Pakistan: An Experimental but Limited Approach

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Abstract

We examined the effect of ALP (adaptive learning platforms) on students' cognitive abilities. The ALP acts as an AI (artificial intelligence) tool. From cognitive abilities we mean three levels of abilities i.e., Understanding level, Applicative Level and Analytical Level. Randomized Pre-Test Post-Test Control Group design was incorporated. All undergraduate students enrolled at Govt. Zamindar Postgraduate College, Gujrat & Chenab Postgraduate College, Gujrat, in the subject of Educational Psychology in session 2023-2024 were the population of the study. Two intact groups; experimental and control groups were taken and randomly assigned after the pre-test as control and experimental groups. A test aligned with the basic sub-levels of cognitive domain was constructed to measure students' cognitive abilities. A validated test was administered to both the groups. Students of experimental group were taught through adaptive learning platforms (a tool of AI) while control group was taught through traditional teaching methods. After manipulation of treatment for two weeks, post-test was applied to both the groups. Data were studied through t-test for each cognitive ability. Based on the results, it is concluded that ALP (adaptive learning platforms) are more effective for developing students' understanding level, applicative ability and analytical level of the undergraduate students. The study results were discussed considering the previous literature. Recommendations were given based on the limited study results

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Introduction

Whenever we talk about AI, creativity emerges. AI and creativity are the sides of one coin, both focusses on newness and originality (Kamran, 2018). Creativity is the same as AI. Artificial intelligence (AI) has performed as a power across numerous areas, altering the learning methods. The field of education has seen mainly rapid integration of AI platforms, reshaping traditional teaching paradigms. One of the most significant innovations brought about by AI in education is the development of adaptive learning systems—platforms designed to personalize the learning experience based on individual learners' needs, preferences, and performance. These systems represent a revolutionary shift in educational practices by offering personalized instruction that adjusts in real time, thereby enhancing student engagement and academic success. Adaptive learning Platform from now will be written as ALP while TTM will be used for traditional teaching methods. As shown that ALP is the learning technology that helps the students in a more flexible way

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than the TTM, the reason is that ALP makes the learning more feasible, customized and more adaptive to the situation where the students want to fit in. The ALP discourages the thinking process that says one size fits all.

The ALP approach determines the students' weaknesses and strength based on AI preferences and makes the learning more individualized and personalized (Gupta, 2023). Even the global transition of TTM to online mode made it more effective and the Higher Education Institutions have advised us to focus on online learning mode rather than TTM. The learning Management System LMS is the combination of tools like Moodle, Black Board, WebCT and Canvas which make learning more flexible, accessible, attentive and individualized (Dunn & Kennedy, 2019) but it has also mismatched and disadvantages when it comes to real classroom settings.

The studies have shown that if the students are not physically located then here comes the role of AI-enables learning approaches (i.e., ALP approaches) which make the learning accessible at a reach of clicks (Tan et al. 2022). The personalized learning approaches (ALP approaches) enable the students to understand deeper cognitive concepts and address the real-life challenges which means that it promotes the students' cognitive developments (Kay & Kummerfeld, 2014).

The study examines the effects of ALP on the cognitive abilities (understanding, application and analysis level) of the students in higher education i.e., the college students before and after the use of ALP. The mentioned cognitive abilities address the students' higher order thinking. For the experimental design the authors divided the participants into two groups, i.e., a control group who were taught through TTM while the experimental group who were taught through ALP by controlling the extraneous and intervening variables. It has also been stated that overreliance on one AI tool might stop the cognitive capability of students because of their frequent use and might leave the students on AI tools only (Selwyn, 2016) but the ALP is only personalized and individualize the learning rather than replacing the human effort. AI integration and human effort should be balanced (Holmes et al. 2019).

Objectives of the Study

- i. To study the influence of ALP on Cognitive levels of Students at undergraduate level.
- ii. Find out the difference in overall mean scores of students' cognitive abilities at undergraduate level taught through TTM and ALP.

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between undergraduates' pre-tests and post-tests mean score regarding their understanding ability taught through ALP.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between undergraduates' pre-tests and post-tests mean score regarding their applicative ability taught through ALP.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference between undergraduates' pre-tests and post-tests mean score regarding their applicative ability taught through ALP.

H₀₄: There is no significant difference in overall mean scores of undergraduates' pre-tests and post-tests in cognitive abilities (including three levels) taught through ALP and TTM.

Literature Review

Adaptive learning is a learning approach which works based on students' preferences, students input (Siemens, 2013). It differs from TTM in the way that ALP offers students autonomy based on the students' pathways. The ALP is very relevant to the constructivist philosophy where the students and teachers actively engage themselves in constructing knowledge relevant to students' cognitive abilities.

The ALP has been mentioned by different researchers (Gupta, 2023) in which it was stated that the ALP promotes the students' engagements with the subject and offers more differentiated learning approach which bridges the learning gaps.

AI tools mostly are used in contexts where the students are not physically present and help in promoting collaborative learning (Tan et al. 2022). Such tools help the students to be immersed in content and

with their peers. Such tools e.g., ALP engages the students into learning and enhances the students' cognitive abilities (Tan et al. 2022). ALP promotes the higher order thinking skills in the students- the understanding, application and analysis levels of Bloom's Taxonomy (Shute & Rahimi, 2017) for which this study has been designed. It has been shown through studies that AI tools are transforming the educational system into a very new trend by making the education individualized and personalized (Smith, 2020) which enhances the cognitive abilities. But Smith (2023) also opines that these tools must be balanced between the automated system and human effort. Teachers should use the AI tools but not replace human behavior.

Here comes two viewpoints, one is saying that frequent trust on AI tools might kill the human effort and may shake the cognitive abilities (Selwyn, 2019) while the other says that AI tools should use as an integrating system but shouldn't completely exchange the TTM (Holmes et al., 2019).

They can identify patterns in student behavior, highlight strengths and weaknesses, and provide tailored recommendations for educators. This iterative feedback benefits both learners and instructors by creating a more responsive and supportive educational environment. In conclusion, the existing literature strongly supports the possibility of adaptive learning platforms to enhance student engagement, personalize instruction, and improve cognitive development, particularly in understanding, applying, and analyzing information. However, successful implementation demands thoughtful pedagogical integration and human oversight. As higher education continues to evolve, ALP stands out as promising tools that can significantly enrich the teaching and learning experience.

Research Design

This study is experimental in nature, having two variables in the study. The first independent variable is ALP while the dependent variable is cognitive abilities of students. ALP is a type of interactive learning that meets individual requirements through learning paths, effective feedback, and extra resources (Kurt, 2021). Researchers investigated the effect of ALP as a tool of artificial intelligence on students' understanding, applicative, and analytical abilities. Randomized Pre-Test Post-Test Control Group design was applied to conduct this study. Two parallel groups were taken to compare the effect of the two teaching methods given. Students of experimental group were taught through ALP while control group students were taught TTM. Experimental research design is illustrated in the following table.

Table *Randomized Pre-test Post-test Control Group Design*

Experimental Group	Pre-test	ALP (IV)	Post-test
Control Group	Pre-test	TTM (DV)	Post-test

Research Treatment

All the undergraduates who were studying 'education as a subject' at Govt. Zamindar Postgraduate College Gujrat & Chenab Postgraduate College Gujrat enrolled in the subject of Educational Psychology session 2023-2024 were the population of the study. Random Sampling technique is used for this study. This study is experimental in nature, and both colleges offer the same subject. To save time, instruction occurs for the control group at Chenab Postgraduate College during the morning session and for the experimental group at Zamindar Postgraduate College in Gujrat during the evening session. Two groups are randomly assigned, providing flexibility in designating either as the control or experimental group, which optimizes time efficiency. A challenge arises in locating a college with a total class strength of sixty students. The difference in pre- and post-mean scores between the groups enhances the potential power for a comprehensive comparative analysis. A total of sixty undergraduate students were randomly selected for the study, resulting in the formation of two equal groups based on random assignment.

The first group was experimental while the second group was control group. Each group consisted of 30 students. In randomization every student has an independent and equal chance of being selected in experimental or control group (Fraenkel et al., 2018). Sample diagram is given in the following.

Table *Sample Diagram*

Sixty students of undergraduate program	R Random assignment of 30 students in Experimental Group	O Pretest: Cognitive abilities test (DV)	X Treatment: Adaptive learning platform	O Post test: Cognitive abilities test (DV)
	R Random assignment of 30 students in Control Group	O Pretest: Cognitive abilities test (DV)	C Traditional Method	O Post test: Cognitive abilities test (DV)

A test of 42 marks was developed to assess the participants’ cognitive abilities in the subject of Educational Psychology. After expert evaluation 29 MCQs were correct to access the student’s cognitive abilities. Weak MCQs were revised. The final test consists of 30 MCQs which include three abilities i.e., understanding ability, applicative ability, and analytical ability. Table of specification was developed, 10 MCQs against each cognitive ability were developed. The test was validated through expert opinion and was distributed to 14 experts to get their opinion. Content Validity Ratio (CVR) and Index (CVI) of the test was calculated, i.e., 0.92. Moreover, MCQs with weak Content Validity Ratio (CVR) were refined and changes were made according to the opinion of the experts.

Table *Content Validity*

Sr. No.	MCQ No.	CVR	Sr. No.	MCQ No.	CVR
1	1	0.86	17	17	0.86
2	2	1	18	18	0.86
3	3	1	19	19	1
4	4	1	20	20	1
5	5	0.86	21	21	1
6	6	0.73	22	22	1
7	7	0.86	23	23	0.86
8	8	1	24	24	0.86
9	9	0.73	25	25	1
10	10	1	26	26	0.86
11	11	1	27	27	0.73
12	12	0.86	28	28	0.86
13	13	0.86	29	29	1
14	14	1	30	30	1
15	15	1	31	CVI	
16	16	1		27.65/30 = 0.92	

Reliability of the Tool

Reliability of test items through Cronbach Alpha was calculated after receiving test responses. The value of the Cronbach Alpha was .78 which confirms the reliability of the test.

Intervention of the Study

Researchers held three sessions with the teachers already teaching at the said colleges for their guidance to conduct the experiment, including one with the supervisor. They were trained particularly in the intervention to teach students through TTM and ALP. Students of experimental group were taught through hands-on activities (activities are performed in computer lab & provide all facilities i.e., PC which has already installed ALP tool & Internet) based on ALP focusing on the following content of Educational Psychology:

- iii. Introduction to Educational Psychology
- iv. Learning Theories
- v. Cognitive Approach
- vi. Behavior Approach
- vii. Evaluation Methods

Furthermore, control group students were taught TTM. This treatment continued for two weeks starting from 27/08/2024 till 06/09/2024.

Results of study

Table Undergraduate pre & post-tests mean scores regarding their students' understanding ability in the subject of educational psychology taught through ALP

ALP Method- students' understanding ability	N	M	SD	df	t-value	Sig.
Pre-test	30	4.8	1.40	29	15.35	0.00
Post-test	30	8.7	0.84			

* p < .05

Results showed a significant difference between pre-test (M = 4.37, S.D. = 1.40) and post-test (M = 8.7, S.D. = 0.84; t(15.35) p = .00 < .05). Hence, H₀₁, i.e., there is no significant difference between undergraduates' pre-tests and post-tests mean scores regarding their understanding ability taught through ALP, is rejected. It revealed that undergraduate students' understanding ability improved after manipulating the independent variable.

Table Undergraduate pre & post-tests mean scores regarding their students' applicative ability in the subject of educational psychology taught through ALP

ALP Method- students' applicative ability	N	M	SD	df	t-value	Sig.
Pre-test	30	4.5	1.40	29	10.69	.00
Post-test	30	8.67	1.182			

* p < .05

Results showed a significant difference between pre-test (M = 4.5, S.D. = 1.40) and post-test (M = 8.67, S.D. = 1.182; t(10.69) p = .00 < .05). Hence, H₀₂ is rejected that there is no significant difference between undergraduates' pre-tests and post-tests mean gain score regarding their applicative ability taught through ALP. It revealed that undergraduate students' applicative ability improved after manipulating the independent variable.

Table Undergraduate pre & post-tests mean scores regarding their students' analytical ability in the subject of educational psychology taught through ALP

ALP Method- students' analytical ability	N	M	SD	df	t-value	Sig.
Pre-test	30	4.16	0.95	29	18.247	.000
Post-test	30	8.93	0.86			

* p < .05

Results showed a significant difference between pre-test (M = 4.16, S.D. = 0.95) and post-test (M = 8.93, S.D. = 0.86; t(18.247) p = .00 < .05). Hence, H₀₃ is rejected that there is no significant difference between undergraduates' pre-tests and post-tests mean score regarding their analytical ability taught through ALP. It revealed that undergraduate students' analytical ability improved after manipulating the independent variable.

Table Overall undergraduate pre & post-tests mean scores regarding their students' cognitive abilities (including three levels) in the subject of educational psychology taught through ALP and TTM

Variable	N	M	SD	f	t-value	Sig.
ALP	30	26.27	1.9	58	18.065	.000
TTM	30	15.9	2.4			

* p < .05

Results showed a significant difference between pre-test (M = 26.27, S.D. = 1.9) and post-test (M = 15.9, S.D. = 2.4; t (18.065) p = .00 < .05). Hence, H₀₄ is rejected that there is no significant difference between undergraduates 'students' cognitive abilities.

Discussion

The findings highlight the significant benefits of using ALP for the instruction of educational psychology. The research revealed that students who engaged with ALP demonstrated a markedly improved understanding of educational psychology concepts, confirming previous findings such as those by Cavanagh and McCarthy (2018), who emphasized the positive impact of adaptive systems on knowledge retention. This study affirms that ALP provides a more efficient strategy than TTM, particularly in fostering comprehension of difficult concepts. Furthermore, the study observed a significant improvement in the students' applicative skills through adaptive learning, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The personalized feedback and tailored practice offered by adaptive platforms appear to enhance the application of theoretical knowledge, bridging the gap between theory and practice. These findings are consistent with prior research (K-12 Education, 2021), which emphasized the benefits of individualized learning experiences in skill development.

Analytical skills were also positively affected, with the study demonstrating that students using ALP showed notable improvement in higher-order cognitive functions. This aligns with Anderson and Krathwohl's (2001) work, suggesting that adaptive platforms, through challenge-based tasks and timely feedback, support critical thinking and problem-solving abilities. The rejection of the null hypothesis in this regard further strengthens the case for adaptive learning's effectiveness in developing analytical capacity.

When comparing adaptive learning with traditional instruction, a clear advantage emerged in favor of the adaptive approach. While TTM provided some conceptual awareness, the impact was not significant. This supports Hattie's (2009) assertion that conventional methods often fail to produce strong perceptual or cognitive gains. Similarly, although traditional approaches offered slight improvements in applicative and analytical skills, they fell short when compared to the personalized and dynamic nature of adaptive systems. Schulman (2004) and Bloom (1984) had previously noted the limitations of traditional instruction in fostering deep application and analysis, a point that this study reinforces.

A significant difference was also found in post-test scores related to comprehension, with adaptive learning yielding higher gains. This outcome supports the conclusions of Pashler et al. (2007), who found adaptive strategies to enhance both understanding and performance more effectively than traditional methods. In terms of application ability, the results showed that ALP led to significantly improved outcomes, again rejecting the null hypothesis and aligning with Lovett et al. (2016), who highlighted the strength of personalized learning environments.

The comparison of post-test scores related to analytical ability further confirmed the superiority of adaptive learning. The large effect size observed validates earlier findings by Mayer and others who advocated adaptive methods in developing analytical skills. Lastly, the study confirmed that adaptive learning had a more profound impact on overall cognitive ability compared to traditional approaches. According to Moreno and Mayer (2007), this is likely due to the customized challenges and feedback that support individual cognitive development—an insight that this study strongly supports.

Conclusion

There is a clear increase in the cognitive abilities of the students through ALP. ALP has been helpful to enhance students' understanding of the various concepts of educational psychology like definitions, and methods commonly used in the field of psychology. Further students' performance on the test results showed that they developed their better understandings in various schools of psychology regarding the similarities and differences as well as their aptness to practical aspects in the field of education. Post-test results showed that students using ALP achieved higher scores in cognitive domains than those taught through traditional methods. The personalized and dynamic feedback provided by ALP played a key role in enhancing their lower order as well as higher order thinking abilities. The results showed a significant rise among the students' comprehension of the process and principles of various theories of educational psychology using ALP. This finding aligns with the hypothesis that ALP can enhance understanding by presenting the learning contents to individual learners' learning styles and their learning needs. Furthermore, the students taught through ALP showed significant increase in attempting the test tasks related to application of concepts and their analytical descriptions.

Similarly, it can safely be concluded that AI-driven learning environments are supportive for the learning of higher-order thinking skills, allowing learners to apply and analyze information more effectively in their practical experiences. As far as the traditional teaching is concerned, particularly in understanding and applicative abilities, the gains were not much promising compared to ALP at the intermediate level. Hence IT based methods are effective, and flexible, that offer greater opportunities for students' cognitive development in modern educational settings. The research also found that ALP were particularly useful in identifying and addressing individual students' needs, weaknesses and motivations, to address the learning gaps more effectively as compared to the traditional use of routine teachings.

Conclusively integrating ALP can meet diverse learning needs and ensure achievement of target learning outcomes among the digital age learners. Overall, it is concluded that there are various advantages of adopting ALP in higher education to enhance student engagement and success in different subjects which ultimately increase their maximum interest and engagement. The results provide a sufficient base for a paradigm shift towards more state of the art and individualized teaching strategies to motivate and effectively engage students in the teaching learning process.

Limitations and Implications for Future Researchers

The study is limited to the city of Gujrat only in Punjab province of Pakistan. Since the study was conducted in the two post graduate colleges of Gujrat and the population wasn't diverse in nature, thus it may hinder the generalization of the results over the general population in the country. To the future researchers, it is recommended to conduct the same or different studies of a more diverse nature by recruiting diverse population to minimize the limitations authors faced in this study

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